

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

One video per demonstrator for the Open Days

Deliverable 7.5

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Author(s)	Charlotte François (EQY)
Primary Contact and Email	Charlotte François – charlotte.francois@euroquality.fr
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

PROJECT PARTNERS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. TRANSFORMAR OPEN DAYS	5
1. MUNICIPALITY OF EGALEO	5
2. ORISTANO	7
3. CITY OF LAPPEENRANTA	8
4. WESTCOUNTRY REGION.....	10
6. GALICIA REGION	12
ANNEX 1. AGENDA OF THE ORISTANO OPEN DAY.....	15
ANNEX 2. LOCAL COMMUNICATION IN PRESS MEDIA IN GALICIA	16

PROJECT PARTNERS

No	Participant organisation English name	Acronym	Country
1	University of Antwerp	UA	Belgium
2	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change	CMCC	Italy
3	ACTIERRA	ACTIERRA	France
4	E3-Modelling	E3M	Greece
5	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	PIK	Germany
6	Verhaert New Products and Services nv	VERHAERT	Belgium
7	Fundación Empresa – Universidad Gallega	FEUGA	Spain
8	National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos”	NCSR	Greece
9	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague	CZU	Czech Republic
10	LUT University	LUT	Finland
11	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	NTNU	Norway
12	University of Vigo	UVIGO	Spain
13	Epsilon Malta Ltd	EPSILON	Malta
14	French Ecological Transition National Agency	ADEME	France
15	Westcountry Rivers Trust	WRT	United Kingdom
16	Mediterranean Sea and Coast	MEDSEA	Italy
17	CETMAR	CETMAR	Spain
18	City of Lappeenranta	LAPP	Finland
19	Municipality of Egaleo	MOE	Greece
20	Water Europe	WE	Belgium
21	Euroquality	EQY	France
22	Gjøvik municipality	MOG	Norway

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This short report provides key information on the organization and impact of six local Open Days that were organized between June and September 2024 in each project Demonstrator territory. These local dissemination events were organized to showcase the local adaptation solutions co-designed and tested in the project.

Direct links to the six videos are also provided in this document.

1. TransformAr Open Days

In total, six Open Days were organised by Demonstrators between June 2024 and September 2024 (one Open Day per Demonstrator), with the support of EQY and local project partners. These Open Days were used as key local dissemination events to showcase local adaptation solutions that were co-developed and implemented during the project to local citizens, media, solution providers, policy makers and change agents.

The agenda of the Oristano Open Day is provided in Annex 1 to provide an example of a possible format and topics that were discussed with local stakeholders and citizens. All agendas were prepared in the local languages of Demonstrators.

The first three Open Days were EU Green week partner events, on the overall theme of Water Resilience. They happened between June and August 2024. The remaining 3 Open Days were all held in September 2024.

Each Open Day is briefly presented in the sections below, with direct links to videos that were made to document the Open Day and local solutions short presentations. All Open Day videos are in Demonstrators' local languages with English subtitles provided when needed to ensure other regions and communities can get inspired. All Open Days videos are available on the TransformAr YouTube channel (direct [link](#)).

1. Municipality of Egaleo

The Municipality of Egaleo's Open Day was held on June 4th 2024, co-organised between MOE and their local Technical support partner NCSR D at the local Climate Innovation Hub. The event gathered 30 participants over half a day. Adaptation solutions for climate awareness, smart climate stations, demand for social services and a citizen app were presented and discussed with local citizens.

The highlight of the event was the participation of local school students, who showcased their own environmental projects. These projects reflected their commitment to sustainability and creative solutions to pressing environmental challenges. As part of the day's activities, a hackathon on climate change was organized, where students enthusiastically collaborated to develop innovative ideas addressing the effects of climate change. Their participation demonstrated their growing awareness of environmental issues and eagerness to contribute to real-world solutions.

The success of the Open Day, combined with the ongoing educational programs, plays a crucial role in enhancing the environmental awareness of younger generations. Through these initiatives, TransformAr contributed to the fostering of a new generation that is ready and equipped to face the impacts of climate change with knowledge and maturity.

By directly engaging local youth and citizens in solution co-creation, the event laid the groundwork for deeper community involvement in future climate adaptation efforts. It also strengthened local ownership and awareness, increasing the chances of long-term integration of these solutions into municipal policies and practices.

Resources on the Egaleo Open Day:

The municipality of Egaleo directly communicated on its website about the event: direct [link](#).

Article published on the TransformAr website: direct [link](#).

Open Day video: direct [link](#).

TransformAr Open Day – City of Egaleo: Showcasing Climate Resilience Solutions

Figure 1. Screenshot of the Open Day video.

Figure 2. Students at the Open Day organised in Egaleo.

2. Oristano

The Oristano Open Day was organised on July 5th and 6th 2024 at the Museum of Marceddì, organised by MEDSEA with the support of CMCC. The event gathered around 50 participants over two half-days. Adaptation solutions for the area were presented and discussed with local citizens, regional policy makers, local representatives and young people. Solutions presented included the smart gate and the coastal contracts, and a focus on wetland and lagoons as local nature-based solutions to adapt to climate change.

On the evening of July 5th 2024, participants followed the nature and environmental tour with environmental in the San Giovanni pond and the Marceddì lagoon, with a visit to the Torre Vecchia, opened for the occasion. On the following day, at the Museo del Mare on Via Lungomare 49, there was a public presentation of the solutions developed in the TransformAr project and the “Laguna ABitata” project exhibition created as part of the educational activities of the School of Architecture of Cagliari.

Simultaneously, between the Museo del Mare and the Marceddì pine forest, a children’s workshop on water quality and birdwatching was held.

Resources on the Oristano Open Day:

Article published on the TransformAr website: direct [link](#).

Open Day video: direct [link](#).

TransformAr Oristano Open Day: Climate Adaptation & Solutions for the Future

Figure 3. Screenshot of the Open Day video.

Figure 4. Local citizens at the Open Day organised in Sardinia.

3. City of Lappeenranta

The City of Lappeenranta Open Day was hosted on August 29th 2024 during the local Greenreality festival. The event gathered 150 participants over the whole day. Solutions for adaptation via a local citizen app, improved stormwater management and NBS were presented and discussed with local citizens and school children.

Visitors to the TransformAr stand had the opportunity to learn about the project's outcomes firsthand. At the Koulukatu demonstration site, LAPP offered interactive presentations to school children and other attendees, highlighting the features of the bio-infiltration area. Over at Central Park, guests could actively participate in citizen science activities. LAPP team members demonstrated how to use the water research kit provided to local schools and guided participants through the process of collecting and analyzing water samples.

The event sparked people's interest in stormwater management. The nature-based solutions area built in the city center had already attracted the attention of local residents, and guided tours of the area helped residents understand how it works and why it was built.

Resources on the Lappeenranta Open Day:

The city of Lappeenranta issued a press release in Finnish, prior to the event.

Article published on the TransformAr website: direct [link](#).

Open Day video: direct [link](#).

TransformAr Project Open Day Highlights | Lappeenranta Greenreality Carnival 2024

Figure 5. Screenshot of the Open Day video.

Figure 6. Open Day stand at the Greenreality festival in Lappeenranta.

4. Westcountry region

The Westcountry region Open Day was held on September 13th 2025 at the Printworks in Tavistock. The event gathered approximately 30 participants over half a day. Solutions for adapting catchment management to climate change risks were presented and discussed with local citizens, academia stakeholders and regional and national representatives of the Environment Agency, Natural England, regional Catchment Partnerships, South West Water.

Attendees engaged in discussions about the project's progress and the Westcountry regional-level work, followed by a visit to the Shorts Down site to explore Natural Flood Management features.

Resources on the Westcountry Open Day:

Article published on the TransformAr website: direct [link](#).

Open Day video: direct [link](#).

Innovating Catchment Management Solutions TransformAr Open Days in the Westcountry Region

Figure 7. Screenshot of the Open Day video.

Figure 8. Participants attending a presentation at the Open Day in Wescountry region.

5. Guadeloupe archipelago

The Guadeloupe archipelago Open Day was held on September 17th 2024 in Guadeloupe. The event gathered 38 participants over half a day. The Local Adaptation Fund and the role of nudging solutions for adaptation in the tourism and agricultural sectors were presented and discussed with local representatives of the private sector, public entities and associations.

The seminar aimed to address the challenges of climate change in the agricultural and tourism industries, with a strong focus on financing strategies and raising awareness of sustainable practices. Attendees engaged in thought-provoking discussions and roundtables on various topics, including:

- The importance of deploying digital tools, such as early warning systems for managing groundwater and guiding agricultural practices.
- Promoting climate-smart crops, particularly vanilla, in agroecology and agroforestry.
- Strengthening networks to support water management and sustainable agricultural practices.
- Prioritizing resilient local breeds to adapt to rising temperatures and meet food security needs.

Key outcomes from the event include strategies for fostering greater cooperation among stakeholders to finance and implement adaptation projects. Discussions emphasized the importance of engaging local support, securing private investments, and developing policies to ensure long-term sustainability.

Resources on the Guadeloupe Open Day:

Communication on social media was made by ADEME after the event: [direct link](#).

Article published on the TransformAr website: [direct link](#).

Open Day video: [direct link](#).

TransformAr Open Day – Guadelupe: Climate Change Adaptation in Agriculture & Tourism

Figure 9. Screenshot of the Open Day video.

Figure 10. Participants of the roundtable during the Open Day in Guadeloupe.

6. Galicia region

The Galicia region Open Day was held on September 18th 2025 at at the Villagarcía de Arousa Auditorium. The event gathered 35 participants over half a day. Solutions for the adaptation of the aquaculture sector were presented and discussed with local representatives of mussel and clam productive sectors, research institutions, socioenvironmental organizations, and government bodies.

The day began with an inaugural address the Conselleiro do Mar (Regional Ministry of Galicia), followed by a welcome and an outline of the day's objectives, in which the importance of collaboration to drive adaptation efforts in Galicia's bivalve mollusc production management was stressed.

The presentations about TransformAr and the local climate risks were made, after which our roundtable to discuss the local TransformAr solutions was organised. A debate and closing sessions then followed to conclude the day, emphasizing the importance of collaboration in co-developing solutions for the challenges ahead. In the interactive session on perception and impact, attendees participated in a Q&A session, where they provided their thoughts on how these solutions could address current and future challenges in aquaculture. A key theme that emerged was the need to strike a balance between innovation, technology, and proactive policymaking to ensure sustainable practices.

The event attracted considerable media attention, with several news outlets covering it, including television news broadcasts and radio segments. The presence of the Conselleiro do Mar was a key factor driving this wide coverage.

Resources on the Galicia Open Day:

Many local press communications and articles were coordinated locally by CETMAR to share the Open Day that was organised. The local media which included a publication on the event included: EUROPA PRESS, FARO, IPAC, LA VOZ DE AROUSA, LA VOZ DE GALICIA and Hoy por Hoy Arosa. One is included in Annex 2 of this deliverables to provide an example. Also, a news video from Vivir o Mar also featured extract on the event: [direct link](#).

Article published on the TransformAr website: [direct link](#).

Open Day video: [direct link](#).

TransformAr Open Day: Climate Adaptation Solutions for Galicia's Mussel and Clam Sectors

Figure 11. Screenshot of the Open Day video.

Figure 12. Participants of the Open Day in Galicia.

ANNEX 1. Agenda of the Oristano Open Day

EU Green Week
PARTNER EVENT

TransformAr Open Day Oristano

Esploriamo la resilienza climatica

Museo del mare,
Marceddì
05 Luglio 2024

#WaterWiseEU

PROGRAMMA

16:30 LABORATORI INTERATTIVI PER BAMBINI

I bambini parteciperanno ad un laboratorio educativo sul tema del risparmio dell'acqua, sulla necessità di preservarne la qualità e sul godersi responsabilmente le zone umide. L'obiettivo è quello di stimolare riflessioni su come i comportamenti umani influenzano l'uso dell'acqua e incoraggiare i bambini a essere consapevoli della loro impronta ecologica – il segno che ognuno di noi lascia sul pianeta con le proprie azioni quotidiane.

Le attività verranno realizzate in parte all'interno del museo, in parte all'aperto nei pressi del museo. Durante il laboratorio sarà prevista una merenda per i bambini.

17:00 TOUR GUIDATO A PIEDI

Tour guidato a piedi intorno alla laguna per approfondire il suo significato ecologico, gli habitat, la biodiversità, le minacce e le tecnologie trasformative che vengono implementate. Questo tour immersivo è progettato per fornire ai partecipanti una comprensione diretta di questo vitale ecosistema acquatico e delle sfide in corso e future, nonché delle misure di adattamento agli impatti dei cambiamenti climatici.

18:30 INSTALLAZIONE E APERITIVO

La serata prosegue con un momento di confronto sui cambiamenti climatici, sulle minacce ambientali attuali e sul percorso intrapreso dal progetto TransformAr, illustrato attraverso poster e immagini che raccontano le soluzioni applicate. In questa sessione verranno presentati i risultati prodotti dagli studenti del corso di laurea triennale in Scienze dell'Architettura dell'Università di Cagliari nell'ambito del laboratorio di progettazione «Laguna Abitata», interamente dedicato a Marceddì.

REGISTRATI QUI: [//bit.ly/TransformAr](https://bit.ly/TransformAr)

A CURA DI:

IN COLLABORAZIONE CON:

ANNEX 2. Local communication in press media in Galicia

2= **AROUSA**

arousa@farodevigo.es
FARO DE VIGO
JUEVES, 19 DE SEPTIEMBRE DE 2024

La comunidad científica lucha contra el cambio climático a partir del mejillón y el marisqueo

Galicia se consolida como banco de pruebas a nivel mundial con proyectos como el Transformar, avalado por la Xunta y la Universidade de Vigo ▶ El conselleiro Villares defiende la sostenibilidad de la acuicultura gallega

MANUEL MÉNDEZ
AROUSA

Con la ría cubierta del humo procedente de los incendios de Portugal y sus bateas y bancos marisqueros amaneciendo bajo un sol de color rojizo que quería abrirse paso, Arousa volvió a presentarse ayer como uno de los mejores lugares del mundo en los que desplegar acciones de carácter científico con las que luchar contra el cambio climático.

Lo hizo gracias a un congreso o jornada de trabajo desplegada en Vilagarcía con la que presentar los avances obtenidos con el proyecto Transformar, que financia la UE y se desarrolla en Galicia, Finlandia, Reino Unido, Francia, Italia y Grecia.

Todas ellas regiones "que actualmente enfrentan un desafío común, como son los riesgos relacionados con el agua y los impactos del cambio climático".

En esta iniciativa, que es uno de los programas preparatorios de la Misión de Adaptación al Cambio Climático de la Comisión Europea, participan 22 socios de once países, entre ellos los gallegos Centro Tecnológico del Mar (Cetmar), Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas (IIM-CSIC) y Universidade de Vigo, en colaboración con la Fundación Empresa-Universidade Galega (Feuga).

El mejillón y el marisqueo a pie centran el campo de trabajo de esta investigación que, en palabras del conselleiro de Mar, Alfonso Villares, "sitúa a Galicia como pionera en el ámbito de la promoción sostenible de moluscos bivalvos".

Así lo expuso en la inauguración de la Jornada desplegada ayer en la ciudad vilagarciana, donde "se presentaron los resultados del índice de resiliencia del mejillón y el modelo Interm para los bancos marisqueros, así como las conclusiones de la monitorización de bateas sensorizadas en tiempo real".

Futuro en la costa

Unos trabajos que la Xunta considera "imprescindibles para evaluar los cambios a los que se exponen el clima y los océanos", ya que permiten "ahondar en la sostenibilidad de la explotación de los recursos marinos" y a su vez, "garantizar el futuro de las poblaciones costeras".

A juicio de Villares, "la innovación en el ámbito marino es la pieza angular del avance hacia una mayor resiliencia y sostenibilidad de la acuicultura gallega".

De ahí que aplaudiera la labor de los investigadores que, en cola-

Alfonso Villares, en la presentación en Vilagarcía del proyecto Transformar, ayer. // Iñaki Abella

boración con el sector productor, siguen dando pasos con los que "avanzar en la mejora de la gestión de la producción del mejillón" para, precisamente, ganar "en eficiencia y sostenibilidad".

Observatorio Costeiro

Para ello también resulta crucial disponer de datos como los que ofrece el Observatorio Costeiro de Galicia, los cuales facilitan "el estudio de variaciones de parámetros como la salinidad o la temperatura del agua que, a la postre, resultan vitales para el desarrollo de este tipo de trabajos", sostienen en Mar.

En el Cetmar abundan en ello detallando que el proyecto Transformar, dotado con casi 12 millones de euros, analiza el impacto de las condiciones oceanográficas en la producción de mejillón monitorizando en tiempo real una batea dotada de sensores.

Al mismo tiempo "se analiza la evolución de los bancos de cultivo y marisqueo de almeja a través de un modelo matemático para explorar estrategias de gestión adaptadas e identificar la capacidad de adaptación al cambio y priorizar acciones que deban acometerse".

Con todo ello se quiere "proporcionar soluciones para impulsar la adaptación al cambio climático, promoviendo la innovación cooperativa para activar la transformación social a través de medidas basadas en la naturaleza, las tecnologías innovadoras, los modelos de financiación, seguros y

Bateas de mejillón en la ría de Arousa, cubiertas del humo que llegaba de los incendios de Portugal, ayer. // M.M.

gobernanza, la concienciación y el cambio comportamental".

Todo esto había sido avanzado ya el pasado mes de mayo -también en el Auditorio Municipal de Vilagarcía- por la comunidad científica y el propio Alfonso Villa-

res, quien asistía a la puesta de largo del Transformar y ya incidía entonces en que la innovación es una herramienta estratégica para lograr "una mayor resiliencia y sostenibilidad en la acuicultura gallega".

187.000 euros para modernizar las instalaciones de San Martiño

La Consellería do Mar ha destinado 187.000 euros a la cofradía de pescadores supramunicipal de San Martiño con sede en O Grove y socios tanto de esta localidad como de Cambados, Ribadumia, Meaño y Sanxenxo.

Es un dinero cofinanciado en un 70% por el Fondo Europeo Marítimo de Pesca y Acuicultura (Fempa), correspondiendo el 30% restante a la Xunta, para modernizar las instalaciones de la lonja y las zonas portuarias.

Más concretamente para adquirir 26 mesas de acero inoxidable en las que "realizar en óptimas condiciones sanitarias" las subastas de pescados y mariscos, además de destinarse parte de los fondos a una nueva cámara de fabricación y conservación de hielo "que va a permitir su expedición automática a través de un cajero de autoservicio situado en la parte exterior de la lonja que funcionará mediante tarjetas cuando los clientes se den de alta como compradores en la lonja", explican en el pósto.

Las mismas fuentes destacan que "la construcción de esta nueva cámara de conservación de hielo, va a permitir agilizar el trabajo en la lonja, además de conseguir un uso eficiente de los recursos y un mayor ahorro energético".

En definitiva, que se trata de una subvención más, sumada a las muchas aportadas por Mar en los últimos años, que va a "mejorar las condiciones de trabajo en la lonja y su competitividad respecto a otros puntos de venta".

Eso sin olvidar que las nuevas incorporaciones de material "pueden evitar accidentes de trabajo, además de propiciar una mayor limpieza en la lonja y mejorar la calidad de los productos desembarcados".

Como se decía anteriormente, esta ayuda se suma a otras, como la de 116.000 euros lograda para financiar acciones de lucha contra la basura marina y limpieza o regeneración de bancos marisqueros, o aquella otra que, con un importe idéntico, perseguía mejorar la eficiencia energética, proteger el medio ambiente y garantizar las condiciones de trabajo.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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